

QUIZ**LAST NAME: SHERIFF****FIRST NAME: MOHAMED****PROGRAM CODE: MDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian footnotes reference style

The author used Zotero to insert footnote references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- All are essential characteristics of an academic essay except.**
 - It should have a thesis statement and a compelling argument.
 - It presents or discusses something in a thesis with reasoning and evidence.
 - It does not necessarily require an evidential value to persuade the readers.¹**
 - It should have a thesis statement and a compelling argument.
- Plagiarism is unacceptable in the field of academia. As a student, how would you ensure that your writing is free from plagiarism?**
 - Paraphrase or summarize a piece of work without directly copying verbatim.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

- Properly reference the author or source of every information you used.²**
 - You can borrow ideas from others as long as they are not overused in a piece of work.
 - Not acknowledging your source of information as long as it is done cleverly.
3. **Does an experienced researcher often ask these fundamental questions except?**
- Emotional questions.
 - Rhetorical questions.
 - Practical, conceptual, and applied questions.³**
 - Responsible questions.
4. **At the core of any research, there three fundamental sources of information and they include the following.**
- Primary, secondary, and tertiary sources of information.⁴**
 - Books.
 - Internet.
 - Other documents.

² Ibid., 5–6.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Eighth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 15.

⁴ Ibid., 24–25.

5. **Writing is one of the major problems encountered by most professionals and students. In most cases, the unfamiliar and confusing expressions have produced negative consequences – resulting in a serious misunderstanding between and among people. As a student, how would you ensure that you write and speak very clearly to the comprehension of our audiences?**

- Knowing audiences and what to say to them.
- Defining unfamiliar words and expressions such as slang.
- Developing or creating a sentence outline of your work including organizing paragraphs, and making sure that sentences are shorter.
- All of the above.**⁵

6. **Editing and proofreading are different steps in the process of revising a text. While editing involves major changes to content, structure, and language, proofreading focuses:**

- Content and structure.
- Minor errors and inconsistencies including spelling and punctuation mistakes, typos, capitalization, formatting issues, and inconsistencies.**⁶
- Styles and accuracy of the information being presented.
- To ensure a piece of writing is free from plagiarism.

7. **Composing a research paper is time, focus, and effort-intensive activity that every student must undertake to avoid notable errors in a research paper. All the following are the most common errors made in research papers except.**

⁵ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th Edition (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group), 20, 60, 82, 130, 214.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 83.

- A coherent and logical flow of information.**⁷
 - Grammar, spelling, and inaccurate words.
 - Usage of direct quotes and unnecessary background.
 - Inadequate editing and proofreading.
8. **Citing and referencing is imperative in the process of writing especially in an academic community. Young researchers such as myself are confronted with the question when should we not provide a citation?**
- When you express your ideas, theories, arguments, conclusions.**⁸
 - Whenever you use ideas, theories, facts, experiments, case studies.
 - Adopt another person's research method, survey, or experiment design.
 - Whenever you use statistics, tables, diagrams, drawings, etc.
9. **Punctuation does more than we might think of writing: it changes the pace of reading, it offers sentence complexity and variety, and it clarifies meaning. This brings us to the question thus: When do we use the exclamation mark?**
- Use a semicolon to combine two sentences without linking conjunction.
 - To ask a question.
 - To express sudden feelings or emotions about something.**⁹

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd Ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 5.

⁸ Ibid. 57.

⁹ Tim Cooper et al., *European Commission Style Guide English* (Luxembourg: European Commission, 2011), 19.

To express doubt in a given sentence.

10. **What is the primary reason for the use of gender-neutral language within the European Union?**

For political reasons.

For geographical reasons.

To ensure inclusion, non-discrimination, and ensure equal opportunities for all persons.¹⁰

For reasons of regional integration.

¹⁰ Ibid. 47.

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